

Individual Development Opportunity, Brand Name and Job Satisfaction

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Abstract

Understanding the impact of individual development opportunity and brand name is important for job satisfaction in universities in Vietnam. This paper examines individual development opportunity, brand name and job satisfaction. The study adopts a convenience sampling method to collect data from 800 permanent lecturers in universities Ho Minh Chi City Vietnam. It was observed that individual development opportunity and university brand name have a significant influence on job satisfaction. As a consequence, it is concluded that by recognizing the impact of individual development opportunity and university brand name. The implication of this study is for the university managers which they can enhance the level of job satisfaction among lecturers in Ho Chi Minh in particular and in Vietnam in general.

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INTRODUCTION

In the context of globalization and intense competition, organisations need to implement strategies for attracting, developing and compensating employees' performance at work (Fadeyi, et al., 2018). Besides universities need to adopt practices that will enhance job satisfaction. One such practice is individual development opportunity. Individual development opportunity focus on training and promotion of employees. Training is the process of learning the skills needed to perform a specific job. Advancement is a move to a more important position or job in a company. Training is often grouped with promotion because training usually aims to promote or enhance the ability and performance of the employees (Martensen & Gronholdt, 2006). Investing in people, building and maintaining an enthusiastic workforce have long-term effects on organisations, universities in particular. To improve job satisfaction and provide quality education, universities must build capability to coordinates and manage complexities during strategy development (Nwachukwu et al., 2018). Arguably, a strong brand name may enhance job satisfaction level of employees. A brand is a name, a word, a sign, a symbol, a picture that identifies, identifies the organization. Branding is an important intangible asset for large organizations as well as universities.

In terms of job satisfaction, individual development opportunity and brand name may enhance the university lecturer job satisfaction level as well as the quality of education and research. Job satisfaction is the extent to which an employee perceives and has positive orientations for work in the organization (James, 1997). When an employee feels happy when working, we can say that he or she is satisfied with the job. Besides that, some scholars argue that job satisfaction is an emotive reaction to a job condition, which is often decided by how nicely results meet up or exceed expectations (Luthans, 2005, Manzoor et al., 2011). Several studies have shown that individual development opportunity variables (training and promotion) have positive impact on job satisfaction as pointed out in the studies of Nwachukwu & Chladkova, 2017, Tien & Toi, 2017;, Liem, 2016; Giacometti, 2015, Andrew et al., 2015, Hang & Trang, 2013, Khoi & Nghi, 2014. Yet, there is still more to know concerning how individual development opportunity impacts university lecturers in Vietnam, Ho Chi Minh in particular. To the best of author knowledge, no study has examined the impact of university brand name on job satisfaction of lecturers, especially in Vietnam. In light of the above, this study attempt to fill a gap in the literature by examining the connection between individual development opportunity, university brand name and job satisfaction of lecturers in universities in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. This study enhances our understanding of the role of individual development opportunity and university brand name in enhancing lecturer satisfaction.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Several studies have examined job satisfaction in varying contexts. Maharjan (2012) investigates the relationship between work motivation and job satisfaction of the teachers in Kathmandu. With the convenient sampling technique, the author distributed questionnaires to 150 teachers working in the educational institutions (universities and colleges) in Kathmandu Valley and collected 112 valid questionnaires. By using descriptive statistics and correlation analysis methods, the study suggests a positive relationship between work motivation and job satisfaction of the teachers at colleges and universities in Kathmandu. Although the research has high practical significance, the author only assessed the

relationship between work motivations with the satisfaction of the teachers. The author suggested that colleges should promote job satisfaction of the teachers to improve organizational effectiveness. In the study of microfinance banks in Nigeria, Nwachukwu & Chladkova (2017) finds that training and development has a significant influence on employee satisfaction. They concludes that firms should invest in training programmes (seminars, conferences) to boost employee satisfaction. Similarly, Nutsuklo (2015) explores the factors affecting job satisfaction of the lecturers at High schools in Accra, Ghana. Convenience sampling method was used to select the research sample. There were 155 questionnaires distributed to the teachers at three high schools in Accra but only 120 valid questionnaires were returned. The study used both description and interpolation statistics figures statistics such as frequency, means and standard deviation, including one-way ANOVA for data verification. The results showed that job satisfaction of the teachers is low. Low salary and welfare policy along with poor working are the main reasons why the teachers were dissatisfied with their work at high schools in Accra. The research has important implications for improving condition for the teacher as well as improving teacher satisfaction with the current working position. Giacometti (2015) examines the factors affecting job satisfaction of young lecturers at the educational institutions in Virginia. The researcher distributed a questionnaire to 450 young teachers with working experience of 1-3 years at educational institutions in Virginia. It was observed that factors affecting teacher satisfaction include: welfare, teaching motivation; working conditions; supporting policies; training opportunities; promotion. In which, welfare and compensation are the most influential factors while promotion factors have the lowest impact on the satisfaction of teachers. Empirically, Andrew (2015) studies job satisfaction in the United States and several other countries. The results are as follows: 49% of US workers surveyed thought complete or very comical. Pleased with work, only a very small number of respondents are dissatisfied. Percentage of respondents who are totally or very satisfied with their jobs in other countries are as follows: Denmark is 62%, Japan is 30% and Hungary is 23%. The study identifies factors that enhance job satisfaction: (a) women; (b) work safety; (c) Small workplace; (d) 22 high income; (e) co-worker relationship; (f) less travel time; (g) monitoring issues; (h) relations with the public; (i) Opportunities for further study. In Vietnam, Hang & Trang (2013) examines the factors affecting the satisfaction and loyalty of the teachers, officials at the universities and colleges in Lam Dong province. The research was conducted in two phases, which were preliminary research and formal research based on survey results from 249 samples. The results showed that there are three factors affecting satisfaction, which are training and development, working conditions and relations with superiors. Training and development factors have the greatest impact on satisfaction. The results also showed that satisfaction has a positive linear relationship with loyalty. In the same direction, Khoi & Nghi (2014) explores factors influencing Job Satisfaction of Medical Staff in Can Tho City. The research was conducted with 330 observations of the doctors and nurses at both private and public hospital in Can Tho City. They found that 5 factors (management environment, working facilities, wages, colleagues, training and development) drive the level of health workers' job satisfaction. Liem (2016) assesses job satisfaction of Forest University Teachers. The objective of the study was to use a model of an exploratory factor to determine the factors affecting job satisfaction of the lecturers at the Forestry University. The question tables were sent to 151 faculty lecturers at VNUF by email, 30 of them were randomly selected for in-depth interviews. Statistical tools (exploratory factor analysis, multiple regression analysis, and descriptive statistic) were used to analyze the data and to interpret the results. Research results showed six groups of factors affecting the level of job satisfaction

of the lecturers, including the relationship with colleagues, leadership, job characteristics, personal development, salary and management policies. Meanwhile, working conditions and relationships with students are not related to lecturer's satisfaction. The study also found that lecturers at the Forestry University are quite satisfied with their work. Tien & Toi (2017) analyzes the factors that affect the satisfaction of employees of the HCMC Development Commercial Joint Stock Bank. (HDBank) in Ho Chi Minh. From the results obtained, the study implies some management-related policies that improve employee satisfaction. The research is conducted in two phases: (i) preliminary research phase by a qualitative method in combination with the quantitative method to determine the scale and the formal model; (ii) main research phase: using quantitative research methodology to explore employee opinion on the factors that affect the satisfaction of their work at HDBank. Results show that there are seven factors that affect overall job satisfaction of employees, ranging from the highest to the lowest: (i) recognition of achievement and reward; (ii) colleagues; (iii) working environment; (iv) superior; (v) opportunities for training and promotion; (vi) the nature of the work; (vii) salary. In light of the literature review, the author hypothesizes thus;

H1. Individual Development Opportunity has a positive impact on job satisfaction.

H2. University's brand-name has a positive effect on the lecturer's satisfaction with the job.

Figure 1. Conceptual model of the study variables.

Source: Own (2019)

METHODOLOGY

The author used both qualitative and quantitative method. The population of the study includes all permanent lecturers who are teaching at universities in Ho Chi Minh City in Vietnam. At present, there are about 50 universities in Ho Chi Minh City with more than 3500 permanent lecturers. We selected a sample of 800 participants based on convenience non-probability sampling method. The survey was conducted in May 2018. The questionnaires were distributed to lecturers working in universities in Ho Chi Minh City through two forms, including direct and email sending. Scales are built and developed based on literature. Before formulating the official scale for research objectives, in-depth interviews were conducted to understand the content of concepts and the meaning of words. The observation variables in the questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale with number selection (1) which means "Strongly disagree", number (2) means "Disagree", number (3) means "No opinion", number (4) means "Agree", number (5) means "Strongly agree". To measure individual development opportunity, the author adapted from the studies of Hieu (2013), Nutsuklo (2015), Giacometti (2015), Lien (2017), Ngoc & Oanh (2017). Five questions were used to assess individual development opportunity; I feel satisfied when the school regularly organizes training course for employees, I am satisfied with the school's fair promotion policy, the University has

always provided me with opportunities for personal development such as job rotation, extracurricular activities etc, I am well-oriented and trained to handle my job, I am always encouraged to innovate by immediate supervisor. To measure university brand name, the measurement scales are adapted from Michaels et al. (2000), Ha (2010), Amos et al. (2015). Six questions were used to assess university brand name; I believe in a bright future when working at school, I am proud of the school's image, the school always creates professional and high-quality services/products, the school is highly valued for the quality of training and caring for students, factors of time and funding for higher education development/training are essential to reach higher levels of satisfaction, the bigger the school's reputation is, the more I satisfied with my job. Four questions were used to evaluate job satisfaction; I feel satisfied to work at my organization, I introduce to everyone this is the best place to work, I am very proud to work at the school, my life is guaranteed when working at the School. The Cronbach alpha result for each variable; Job satisfaction had $\alpha = 0.805$, individual development opportunity had $\alpha = 0.877$ and university brand name had $\alpha = 0.912$. The Cronbach alpha results that are more than $\alpha = 0.70$ implies good internal consistency among the items. The analysis results for the independent variable group (individual development opportunity and university brand name) show that the KMO coefficient is 0.831, Bartlet verification for Sig coefficient = 0.000 suggests that the statistical significance level of the results is valid and reliable. The variance is 73.025, indicating that the variation of factors given by factor analysis will explain 73% of the variation of the original survey data. This ratio is very high, suggesting that the given factors have a good representation of the original data, which increases the representative significance of the factors for this data. The factor load factor of each observed variable represents each factor is greater than 0.5, which indicates that the EFA analysis is guaranteed, and has the effect of each variable observed on the factor that the variable that shows. The results for job satisfaction (dependent variable) show that KMO coefficients of 0.710, is higher than 0.5, indicating that the factor analysis results are valid. Bartlet test for Sig. coefficient = 0.000 shows that the variables are correlated in the overall. The variance extract is equal to 50.942, indicating that the variation of factors given by factor analysis will explain greater than 50% of the variation of the original survey data. The research use SPSS and AMOS statistical analysis software to analyze the data. SPSS 22.0 software was used for preliminary evaluation of the scale through Cronbach's Alpha coefficient assay, EFA and sampling descriptive statistics analysis. AMOS 22.0 software was used to analyze CFA. Model and hypothesis were implemented with SEM, model estimation was implemented with bootstrap.

RESULTS

Descriptive statistical analysis

Characteristics of the customers participating in the survey

800 respondents participated in the survey. 772 responses were valid and used for the analyses conducted. Table 1 shows the results of a descriptive statistical analysis of the characteristics of 772 participants.

Table 1: Statistics of surveyed subjects

Gender			
		Frequency	Percent (%)
Valid	Male	401	51.9
	Female	371	48.1
	Total	772	100
Marital status			
		Frequency	Percent (%)
Valid	Single	272	35.2
	Married	500	64.8
	Total	772	100
Age			
		Frequency	Percent (%)
Valid	22 - 29	186	24.1
	30 - 37	264	34.2
	38 - 45	206	26.7
	> 45	116	15
	Total	772	100
Education			
		Frequency	Percent (%)
Valid	Bachelor	0	0
	Master	576	74.6
	PhD.	135	17.5
	Professor.	61	7.9
	Total	772	100
Experience			
		Frequency	Percent (%)
Valid	1 - 3	203	26.3
	4 - 6	246	31.9
	7 - 9	170	22.0
	> 10	153	19.8
	Total	772	100
Organization			
		Frequency	Percent (%)
Valid	Private	410	53.1
	Non-private	362	46.9
	Total	772	100
Field			
		Frequency	Percent (%)
Valid	Economics	427	55.3
	Technology	345	44.7
	Total	772	100
Title			
		Frequency	Percent (%)
Valid	Department Head	74	9.6
	Manager	130	16.8
	Lecturer	568	73.6
	Total	772	100
Income			

		Frequency	Percent (%)
Valid	5 - 8 mil	133	17.2
	9 - 12 mil	285	36.9
	13 - 15 mil	199	25.8
	> 15 mil	155	20.1
	Total	772	100
Where did you study your finishing education?			
		Frequency	Percent (%)
Valid	Local	608	78.8
	Overseas	164	21.2
	Total	772	100
Hometown			
		Frequency	Percent (%)
Valid	Urban	265	34.3
	Village	507	65.7
	Total	772	100

Source: Own (2019)

The survey of respondents showed that the proportion of men accounted for more percentage than women but the difference was not much. Among 772 researched samples, 51.9% were male and 48.1% were female. The research results show that the rate of married teachers is quite high, accounting for 64.8%, reflecting the point that once the lecturers have got a stable career, they tend to pay attention to getting married then. Survey results show that there were 186 lecturers aged from 22 to 29, accounting for 24.1%; 264 lecturers aged from 30 to 37, accounting for 34.2%; 206 lecturers in aged from 38 to 45, accounting for 26.7% of the respondents. In the survey sample, only 15% of the lecturers were over 45 years old. Thus, almost university lecturers in Ho Chi Minh City are in middle age. They are dynamic people with the ability to study and approach new things well and are also mature enough to give reliable answers. Due to the psychological characteristics of middle-aged people, it is easy for the universities to take appropriate measures to improve the level of attachment to the organization. Through the research results, master degree in the education level of the lecturers take the majority rate of 74.6%, followed by the number of lecturers with a doctoral degree is also quite large, accounting for 17.5%. Besides, the number of Associate Professors and Professors participating in teaching, manager at universities in Ho Chi Minh City is only 7.9%, equivalent to 61 people. However, this rate is also quite high compared to the number of Associate Professors and Professors teaching and manager currently. The results showed that there were 203 participants having working time from 1 to 3 years, accounting for 26.3%, 246 lecturers were having 4-6 working year experience, accounting for 31.9%, 170 people with working time from 7-9 years, accounting for 22%. Also, in the survey sample, there were 153 lecturers with more than 10 years of working experience. It can be seen that the number of teaching year experience of the lecturers at universities in Ho Chi Minh City is quite high while the number of new lecturers participating in teaching from 1-3 years only accounts for about $\frac{1}{4}$. In particular, the number of lecturers with more than 10 years of service is quite large, accounting for nearly 20%. Therefore, it can be seen that the teaching experience of the lecturers is quite rich, creating more favourable conditions in teaching. Particularly, the lecturers have been applying practical experience into developing advanced training programs, teaching and learning methods as well as creative thinking methods. Among 772 lecturers, 410 lecturers are working in private universities, accounting for 53.1% and 46.9% of lecturers working in public schools. Thus, there is not much difference in the number of lecturers in public and non-public educational institutions. Thus, the survey

results have high accuracy. The surveyed lecturers are currently teaching and learning in two fields which are economics and technology. In which, 427 lecturers were working in the economic sector, accounting for 55.3% and 44.7% of the lecturers work in the engineering sector with 345 lecturers. The survey sample included lecturers working in various positions. Accordingly, 74 lecturers are holding the positions as heads of faculties and departments, accounting for 9.6%; there were 130 lecturers in management positions and 568 lecturers teaching, accounting for 73.6% of the total number of surveyors. It can be seen that the group with income from 9-12 million VND/month take the majority with 34.6%, the group with income from 5-8 million / month accounted for 17.2%, the group with income from 13-15 million VND/month accounted for 22.8% and the group with an income of over 15 million VND/month accounted for 20.1%. These income levels show that the lecturers teaching at the universities in Ho Chi Minh City have a high-income level. However, the number of the lecturers with average income from 5-8 million VND/month is still quite a lot since most of them are young lecturers and the universities have not paid much attention to paying worthy salary to the lecturers, too. The domestic trained lecturers take the majority percentage with 78.8%, the percentage of foreign-trained lecturers is 21.2%. This shows that the number of lecturers who graduated from foreign training programs also accounts for an increasing proportion of the faculty structure of universities in the city area. This is a clear difference compared to the first years of international integration. The number of lecturers from rural areas takes the majority percentage with 65.7% while the number of lecturers living in the city only accounted for 34.3%.

Table 2: Summary of impact coefficient of factors in an unstandardized model

Dependent variable	Impact direction	Independent variables	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
J_S	<---	I_D_O	0.18	0.014	12.452	***
J_S	<---	U_B	0.138	0.014	10.103	***

Source: Own (2019)

Table 3: Synthesis of the impact coefficient of the factors in the standardized model

Dependent variable	Impact direction	Independent variables	Estimate
J_S	<---	I_D_O	0.386
J_S	<---	U_B	0.288

Source: Own (2019)

The analytical results show that both individual development opportunity and university brand name show significant influence on job satisfaction.

Test bootstrap

With the survey sample size of 772 people, the bootstrap verification was done with a sample size of 1000. The test results are as follows.

Table 4: Estimated results of model coefficient with a sample size of 1000

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
J_S	<---	I_D_O	0.18	0.014	12.452	***
J_S	<---	U_B	0.138	0.014	10.103	***

Source: Own (2019)

Table 5: Deviation of the coefficients of the model with a sample size of 1000

Parameter			SE	SE-SE	Mean	Bias	SE-Bias
J_S	<---	I_D_O	0.02	0.000	0.181	0.001	0.001
J_S	<---	U_B	0.016	0.000	0.138	0.000	0.001

Source: Own (2019)

The results show that the coefficients in the model are not significantly different from the model determined with a sample size of 772. This suggests that the model is consistent with the sample size of 1000 and the estimates in the model can be relied upon.

Summary of hypothesis testing

The hypotheses in the original research model are synthesized after testing as follows:

Table 6: Hypothesis test

Hypothesis	Standardized coefficient	P-values	Conclusion
Individual Development Opportunity has a positive impact on job satisfaction.	0.386	0.000	Supported
University's brand-name has a positive effect on the lecturer's satisfaction with the job.	0.288	0.000	Supported

Source: Own (2019)

The two hypotheses from the theory are supported. Individual development opportunity and university brand name have a strong positive impact on job satisfaction of university lecturers. From testing hypotheses, the author gives a model of synthesizing research results as follows. Hypothesis 1 result is consistent with several other studies that reported positive impact of training and promotion on job satisfaction (Nwachukwu & Chladkova, 2017; Tien & Toi, 2017; Liem, 2016; Giacometti, 2015; Andrew et al., 2015; Hang & Trang, 2013; Khoi Nghi, 2014).

Current situation of Individual Development Opportunity

The Individual Development Opportunity for lecturers is a special activity that is highly regarded by universities because it affects the teaching, prestige and position of the University as well as the level of sticking with the faculty. To assess whether the training and advancement of universities in Ho Chi Minh City meet the teachers' expectations, the author conducted a survey of lecturers' opinions about satisfaction level with individual development opportunity, the results are shown in the following table:

Table 7: Evaluation of lecturers on training and promotion

I_D_O	IV. Individual Development Opportunity	Mean
I_D_01	I feel satisfied when the school regularly organizes training course for employees.	3.6
I_D_02	I am satisfied with the school's fair promotion policy.	3.49
I_D_03	The University has always provided me with opportunities for personal development such as job rotation, extracurricular activities etc.	3.25
I_D_04	I am well-oriented and trained to handle my job.	3.67
I_D_05	I am always encouraged to innovate by immediate supervisor.	3.59

Source: Own (2019)

In general, training courses for lecturers of universities in Ho Chi Minh City are implemented regularly. Content of the survey *"I feel satisfied when organizes training course for employees"* reaches 3.6 points. This shows the concern of the school leaders with the training and capacity building for the faculty. Universities have set aside funding to support teachers going for master and doctoral studies to improve their professional qualifications. Besides, the majority of university lecturers in Ho Chi Minh City feel that the training activities help them handle their jobs better while they are always encouraged to innovate. This is reflected in the survey content which is highly rated with 3.67 points and 3.59 points. But the development of education at the university level is not the same in each department; the selection of teaching staff to study postgraduate programs to improve knowledge is still widespread, not in line with the planning, and organizing pedagogical professional training for newly recruited teachers and lecturers who have not yet received training according to the Ministry of Education and Training's regulations. From this, many dissatisfied lecturers in the university and content training activities *"I am satisfied with the fair promotion policy"* are rated only 3.49 points. Also, there are some limitations for promotion when standards and conditions for consideration and promotion are unclear, formal and general; only regulating qualifications, political qualifications, age and working capacity, so lecturers have no basis to strive to set goals. Conditions for promotion are not attached much to the results of work performance and contributions of employees, mainly those with seniority and prestige will be nominated and appointed. New young lecturers come into teaching even though they are competent but have few opportunities for advancement. Therefore, the fairness of promotion is not highly appreciated by lecturers, so the content *"University has always provided me with opportunities for personal development such as rotation job, extracurricular activities etc"* only reached 3.25 points. Thus, besides the achieved results, there are still many limitations in training and promotion activities for university lecturers in Ho Chi Minh City. This has certain effects on the level of commitment of faculty members at universities.

The status of University's brand-name

University's brand-name is a factor that directly influences the level of employee engagement. The brand creates confidence and pride for employees working at the organization, thereby enhancing the job satisfaction of employees. Survey of faculty members on the university brand where they work, the author obtained the following results:

Table 8: Evaluation of the lecturers about the university's brand-name

U_B	VI. University's brand-name	Mean
U_B1	I believe in a bright future when working at school.	3.32
U_B2	I am proud of the school's image	3.62
U_B3	The school always creates professional and high-quality services/products.	3.35
U_B4	The school is highly valued for the quality of training and caring for students.	3.33
U_B5	Factors of time and funding for higher education development/training are essential to reach higher levels of satisfaction.	3.54
U_B6	The bigger the school's reputation is, the more I satisfied with my job.	3.46

In general, most of the lecturers that participated in the survey are very proud of the image of the university where they work. At the same time, they feel more satisfied with the job when the school brand is popular, the investment activities for higher education are also more

focused. However, the quality of education at universities in Ho Chi Minh City has not been appreciated. Massive training situation does not guarantee the output quality of students. The number of graduates who do not apply for a job or work incorrectly in a major field is very high. This affects the brand of the school as well as influences the commitment of the faculty to the working unit. Thus, the evaluation points for brands of universities in Ho Chi Minh City are not high, the quality of training services is limited. This is a common situation of our education sector today when competition between schools is increasing but competition with human resources, focusing on human resources investment, quality of services and training it is still weak.

The reality of job satisfaction

The commitment of the faculty to the organization is only created when the lecturer is satisfied with the current job. Survey of satisfaction in the work of the faculty, the author obtained the following results:

Table 9: Evaluation of lecturers on job satisfaction

JS	VIII. Job Satisfaction	Mean
JS1	I feel satisfied to work at my organization.	3.54
JS2	I introduce to everyone this is the best place to work.	3.6
JS3	I am very proud to work at the school.	3.56
JS4	My life is guaranteed when working at the School.	3.5

In general, most of the faculty members surveyed are satisfied with the work and positions in universities in Ho Chi Minh City. The survey results show that the teaching staff feel satisfied with their current job, they are proud of the university where they work and they will introduce people to the ideal place to work. Besides, work in universities also creates a stable income to help maintain the lives of faculty. These are factors that create high satisfaction for the lecturers of universities in Ho Chi Minh City, thereby increasing their commitment to the organization of this team.

CONCLUSION

The support of disciplined, hardworking and motivated lecturers is important for universities to achieve their goals. Robust training and promotion policies/culture can foster job satisfaction of university lecturers. Also, a strong brand name can enhance the job satisfaction level of academic staff in universities. The study clarifies the role of individual development opportunity and university brand name in the context of job satisfaction in universities in Vietnam. Our results suggest that individual development opportunity and university brand name significantly impact on job satisfaction. This implies that quality training, promotion and brand name can enhance job satisfaction among lecturers in universities in Vietnam. This paper adds to the existing literature in human resource management/organisational behaviour research by shedding light on the role of individual development opportunity and university brand name play in improving job satisfaction in the university setting. If universities desire to have satisfied lecturers, they need to develop and implement strong training and promotion policies. Also, they must build a strong brand name as this is a driver of job satisfaction. By acknowledging the importance of individual development opportunity and university brand name, universities can significantly job satisfaction. On the other hand, if they pay less attention to individual development opportunity and brand name it may lead to negatively affect job satisfaction. Low job satisfaction may lead to high labour turnover and

cost. This study used samples from universities in Ho Chi Minh City in Vietnam. This may limit the generalisation of the study to all the universities in Vietnam. Future research should extend the study to cover other cities and industry in Vietnam. Nonetheless, the applicability of this study makes both theoretical and practical contribution to the literature.

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